

Motor and visuospatial processing profile in a cross-conditions study: A comparison between developmental coordination disorder and nonverbal learning disability

Ramona Cardillo^{a,b,*}, Camilla Orefice^a, Nicolas Leanza^c, Irene C. Mammarella^a

^a Department of Developmental and Social Psychology, University of Padova, Italy

^b Department of Women's and Children's Health, University of Padova, Italy

^c Foundation IRCCS Cà Granda Ospedale Maggiore Policlinico, Milano, Italy

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Developmental Coordination Disorder
NonVerbal Learning Disability
Developmental Visual Spatial Disorder
Motor abilities
Visuospatial processing

ABSTRACT

Background: Neurodevelopmental conditions often exhibit overlapping symptoms, posing challenges for differential diagnosis. Developmental Coordination Disorder (DCD) manifests as fundamental motor impairments, often along with co-occurring visuospatial difficulties. Nonverbal Learning Disorder (NLD) features visuospatial core challenges, with a less consistent characterization of its motor profile. Strikingly, to date no study has directly compared DCD and NLD profiles.

Aims: The present study aimed to analyze whether DCD and NLD share any characteristics by contrasting their motor and visuospatial performances, comparing them with non-diagnosed (ND) peers.

Methods and Procedures: A total of 102 participants (8–16 years; DCD N = 29, NLD N = 29, ND N = 44) completed motor and visuospatial tasks. The groups' performance was compared, and the discriminatory power of the measures administered was analyzed.

Outcomes and Results: Our findings support the substantial motor and visuospatial impairments in DCD and NLD, respectively. Regarding diagnostic efficacy, motor and visuospatial tasks effectively differentiated DCD or NLD from ND, with specificities related to each condition. Balance, and to a lesser extent, Spatial Processing revealed significant predictive power in distinguishing between DCD and NLD.

Conclusions and Implications: Our results revealed cross-disorder similarities and highlighted specific hallmarks, corroborating the need of a comprehensive motor and visuospatial assessment for distinguishing between DCD and NLD.

What this paper adds?

The present study represents the first attempt to directly compare the profiles of children with a diagnosis of developmental coordination disorder (DCD) or nonverbal learning disability (NLD) on several measures of motor and visuospatial skills. Notably, there has been no prior study offering a thorough assessment of both gross- and fine- motor skills in children with NLD. Our findings uncovered the identification of two distinct profiles among our sample of children with neurodevelopmental

* Correspondence to: Department of Developmental and Social Psychology, University of Padova, Via Venezia 8, Padova 35131, Italy.

E-mail address: ramona.cardillo@unipd.it (R. Cardillo).

¹ orcid.org/0000-0001-6891-0690

disorders: those with balance, gross and fine-motor challenges (i.e., DCD), and those with fine-motor, visuo-motor and visuo-spatial processing difficulties (i.e., NLD). In addition, despite these boundaries between the two conditions, our results suggest that some symptoms commonly associated with one disorder may appear in the other with different degrees of severity, aligning with pre-existing research findings on other neurodevelopmental disorders. Overall, the findings presented in our paper mark progress in comprehending and diagnosing children with either of these conditions.

1. Introduction

Motor abilities are crucial for children's efficient daily functioning (Rosenberg et al., 2017). In everyday life they continuously move around the environment, explore locations, and actively use their bodies to perform several duties, for example getting dressed, picking food up using cutlery, performing school activities (e.g., drawing and writing), participating in sport and recreational events. All these activities rely on the motor domain, which covers a predominant role in the acquisition of adaptive behaviors, independence, and socio-relational skills (Farran et al., 2019).

Motor abilities are classically defined as a series of individual capacities that underlie the performance of a variety of movement skills and have a functional outcome to be realized (Cattuzzo et al., 2016). Fundamental movement skills could be categorized into three different main areas: (i) Manual dexterity, (ii) Object control and Gross Manipulative skills, (iii) Locomotor skills and Balance (De Oliveira et al., 2019; Henderson et al., 2007). Manual dexterity refers to the fine motor control of hands and fingers needed to manipulate objects (Cardillo, Erbi, et al., 2020). Object control and gross manipulative skills, as well as locomotor skills and balance, rely on the activity of large muscles (Cattuzzo et al., 2016; Loprinzi et al., 2015). The former refers to the ability to control tools and objects using the body and consists of the joints performing basic movements (e.g., aiming, throwing, catching with hands or feet) (Staples & Reid, 2010). The latter allows for maintaining a stable body position while performing any kind of task (Bressel et al., 2007).

A neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by fundamental motor impairments in all the three areas above described is the Developmental Coordination Disorder (DCD). Motor skills of individuals with DCD are below expectations for chronological age or learning and use opportunities, thus determining negative outcomes on adaptive functioning (American Psychiatric Association APA, 2013). Along with the core motor features, individuals with DCD often present with co-occurring psychosocial difficulties (Zwicker et al., 2013), as well as cognitive/neuropsychological vulnerabilities, in particular visuospatial impairments (Gras et al., 2023; Wilson et al., 2017).

Visuospatial abilities are human cognitive competences crucially involved in our interaction with the environment and are needed to recognize, process, and mentally manipulate visual and spatial information (Cardillo, Lanfranchi, et al., 2020; Hegarty et al., 2005). Their important involvement in numerous daily and motor activities has been extensively demonstrated (Cameron et al., 2016). In addition, different studies have highlighted the crucial role of motor skills in constraining and guiding the development of visual-perceptual (Corbetta et al., 2000) and visuospatial skills (Hellendoorn et al., 2015; Soska et al., 2010).

Specifically, visual-perceptual difficulties and visuospatial processing deficits have been documented in DCD (Sigmundsson et al., 2003; Wilson et al., 2013), as well as impairments in visuospatial short-term and working-memory (Alloway et al., 2009; Wang et al., 2017). For instance, a recent study, using a cluster analysis on 164 children with a DCD diagnosis, identified a subgroup of children with marked visuospatial impairment (Gras et al., 2023). Alongside these findings, it should be noted that highly heterogeneous profiles of visuospatial abilities have been reported in children with DCD. For instance, Tsai et al. (2008) investigating visual-perceptual abilities in a large DCD sample ($n = 178$) revealed that a highly variable percentage of children with DCD (from 8.4 % to 44.38 %) scored below the 15th percentile on different visuospatial tasks. Heterogeneous performance for children with DCD emerged also on visual-perceptual, visual discrimination and visuo-motor integration tasks (Van Waelvelde et al., 2004). On the other hand, other studies did not find visual-perceptual impairments in children with DCD (e.g., Bonifacci, 2004), and their results suggested that DCD alone is not associated with visual-perceptual problems. From this perspective, the heterogeneity of findings in studies on DCD may be explained by the presence of comorbid developmental disorders (Crawford & Dewey, 2008). Specifically, Crawford and Dewey (2008) emphasized that visual-perceptual difficulties in children with DCD are more strongly associated with coexisting conditions such as ADHD or Reading Disorders. Consistent with the findings of Jongmans et al. (2003), their study showed that the severity of visual perceptual deficits appears to increase with the number of co-occurring disorders, with children diagnosed with DCD, ADHD, and Reading Disorders exhibiting the most significant impairments. These findings support the stance that visuospatial domain in children with DCD has to be considered with attention in experimental and clinical settings, alongside the motor abilities (Tsai et al., 2008).

However, along with the intra-group variability, which has frequently been documented (e.g., Tsai et al., 2008; Van Waelvelde et al., 2004), an in-depth analysis of the literature seems to suggest that methodological differences between the studies design may in part explain the inconsistency of the published results. For example, the past literature frequently featured samples with either small sizes (e.g., Ameratunga et al., 2004; King et al., 2011) or heterogeneous age ranges (e.g., Ameratunga et al., 2004; Crawford & Dewey, 2008; King et al., 2011; Pisella et al., 2020; Tsai et al., 2012). In addition, many differences in the previously published studies emerged in the identification of children with or without a DCD. For instance, several different cut-offs in the Movement Assessment Battery for Children (MABC, Henderson et al., 2007) have been used to identify or exclude the presence of DCD (e.g., Crawford & Dewey, 2008; Van Waelvelde et al., 2004; Wang et al., 2017; Williams et al., 2006). Moreover, in some other studies, in which a population-based sampling was used, a confirmation of the diagnosis upon the DSM (APA, 2013) or ICD (World Health Organization WHO, 2022) criteria was missing. Thus, it is arguable that a large part of these results may come from a population that may exhibit DCD traits (i.e., massive

motor impairment), rather than from a properly defined clinical population (e.g., Tsai et al., 2008, 2012). Moreover, in many of the studies, groups were only matched for age and sex (e.g., Tsai et al., 2012; Van Waelvelde et al., 2004) and not for IQ. In addition, the literature upon the visuospatial profile in DCD may have been complicated by the enclosure of visuospatial weakness as inclusion criteria (e.g., Gras et al., 2023). Finally, as Gras et al. (2023) pointed out, seldom samples are not restricted to children with DCD, but comprised a range of neurodevelopmental disorders (e.g., Crawford & Dewey, 2008; Pisella et al., 2020). Taken together, all these limitations point out the necessity for additional research on visuospatial skills in children with DCD.

Moving on and taking into account the well documented overlapping between neurodevelopmental disorders (Astle et al., 2022), it appears useful to shed light not only on the main symptoms of each disorder, but on the full array. In fact, as highlighted by Annaz et al. (2008) and by Thomas et al. (2009), several characteristic features of one disorder may appear, with a milder presentation, in other disorders (Mammarella et al., 2022). Specifically, alongside DCD, Nonverbal Learning Disorder (NLD) or visual-spatial developmental disorder is a neurodevelopmental condition characterized by deficits in processing and integrating visual and spatial information (Fisher et al., 2022; Mammarella & Cornoldi, 2020). Children with NLD were found struggling with tasks involving visual perception, visuo-constructive skills or visuospatial working memory (Cardillo, Vio, et al., 2020; Mammarella & Pazzaglia, 2010). For the latter domain, its specificity has been well documented by several studies, showing impairments in children with this diagnosis, comparing them with both typically developing peers (Basso Garcia et al., 2014; Cornoldi et al., 1999; Mammarella & Cornoldi, 2005b, 2005a) and children with other neurodevelopmental conditions (Basso Garcia et al., 2014; Cardillo, Lanfranchi, et al., 2020; Mammarella et al., 2019). In addition, the above-mentioned impairments in visuospatial processing may be associated with academic, motor, and even socio-relational problems (Mammarella et al., 2009, 2013, 2022; Petti et al., 2003; Semrud-Clikeman et al., 2014).

To date, the outstanding effort carried out by researchers to better define the characteristics of this condition led to the first NLD Consensus Conference, hosted at the Columbia University (Fisher et al., 2022). As a result, a set of shared criteria for identifying NLD have been defined. The visual-spatial deficits are the hallmark defining feature of the disorder and may affect several areas, such as visuospatial awareness, visuospatial construction, visuospatial memory, visuospatial scanning/tracking, spatial estimation, three-dimensional thinking, and interpreting information presented pictorially (Fisher et al., 2022; Mammarella & Cornoldi, 2020). However, motor coordination skills have rarely been a focus of research studies in NLD (Mammarella, 2022). A recent systematic review (Fisher et al., 2022) reported that a paucity of studies has investigated motor skills of children with NLD focusing only on fine-motor abilities and attaining conflicting results. On the one hand, some studies found no significant differences between NLD and other groups using measures of motor abilities (Chow & Skuy, 1999; Rourke & Strang, 1978; Wilkinson-Smith & Semrud-Clikeman, 2014). On the other hand, other studies found weaknesses in the hands' dexterity and coordination in children with this condition (Durand, 2005; Nichelli & Venneri, 1995; Semrud-Clikeman et al., 2010). In addition, although youths with NLD are often described as clumsy, there are no studies examining their gross motor difficulties, nor studies comparing them with children with DCD (Fisher et al., 2022). Thus, results upon motor skills in NLD are still inconsistent, and further investigations are needed.

Taken together, what we have stated above suggests a partial overlap between the symptom profile of DCD and NLD. Both conditions were found to be associated with motor and visuospatial difficulties, albeit to different extents, leading to challenges in the differential diagnosis and in the definition of strict inclusion/exclusion criteria in the research field. While the literature hints at some overlap between the two conditions, it also reveals a relative lack of characterization - manifested as inconsistent findings or anecdotal evidence - of profiles in domains outside their core symptoms (i.e., the motor domain for NLD and the visuospatial domain for DCD). Since comparisons in these areas represent only a preliminary step toward better defining these profiles, there is a clear need for more comprehensive investigations, which could provide valuable insights for both research and clinical practice. Notably, to date, only one study has directly compared the two profiles (Orefice et al., 2024), highlighting potential distinctive features of each profile and underscoring the need for further research on this topic.

1.1. The present study

The present study represents one of the first attempts to compare DCD and NLD across several measures of motor (i.e., manual dexterity, aiming and catching, and balance) and visuospatial skills (i.e., visual-motor integration, visual-perceptual processing, and spatial processing). Specifically, in order to assess motor abilities, the Movement ABC-2 battery (Henderson et al., 2007) was administered. This test is recognized as the most widely used tool for identifying motor difficulties in children and adolescents (Blank et al., 2019). Thus, in the present study, our objectives were twofold. First, we aimed to gather additional information on these domains within each condition by identifying similarities and differences in performance between the two clinical groups and comparing them to a non-diagnosed (ND) group. Second, we aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of the measures in estimating the discriminatory power of various motor and visuospatial tasks to distinguish between the two clinical groups, as well as between each of them and the ND group.

Based on previous research findings, we expected to confirm the presence of main impairments in the motor domain for the DCD group (APA, 2013) and in the visuospatial domain for the NLD group (Basso Garcia et al., 2014; Fisher et al., 2022; Mammarella et al., 2019; Mammarella & Cornoldi, 2005a). In light of the heterogeneous results in the DCD literature (Bonifacci, 2004; Orefice et al., 2024; Pisella et al., 2020; Tsai et al., 2008; Van Waelvelde et al., 2004), we also expected to find some weaknesses in visuospatial tasks for the DCD group (Wilson et al., 2013), alongside some preserved visuospatial functions (Bonifacci, 2004; Crawford & Dewey, 2008). Given the documented relationship between visuospatial and fine-motor domains (i.e., manual dexterity), we expected to identify difficulties in the latter for children with NLD (Durand, 2005; Nichelli & Venneri, 1995; Orefice et al., 2024; Semrud-Clikeman et al., 2010). As for the gross motor skills and balance, we expected severe difficulties in the DCD group (APA, 2013; Wilson et al., 2013). Nevertheless, the inconsistency of previous reports on these domains (see for a review Fisher et al., 2022) prevented us from making

any specific predictions regarding the NLD group's performance. As for the discriminatory power, we hypothesized that motor and visuospatial skills would accurately differentiate respectively cases of DCD or NLD from typical development, while a lower but still sufficient discriminatory power might be expected for distinguishing between DCD from NLD.

2. Method

2.1. Participants

A total of 102 children (70 males and 32 females, sex assigned at birth), aged between 8 and 16 years old, took part in the study. The sample was split into three groups: DCD ($N = 29$), NLD ($N = 29$), and children neither with DCD nor NLD, and for whom a typical development was assumed, ND ($N = 44$).

Children included in the clinical groups were recruited via local specialized clinical centres. For taking part in the study a Full-Scale Intelligence Quotient above 80 was required. In addition, in order to confirm their intelligence skills, vocabulary and block design of the Wechsler's Intelligence Scale for Children – Fourth Edition (WISC-IV; Wechsler, 2003), were administered. All participants were native Italian speakers with comparable productive and receptive verbal skills, as demonstrated by their scores on the vocabulary subtest of the WISC-IV and the language/communication section of the Autism Diagnostic Interview-Revised (ADI-R; Rutter et al., 2005) parent interview (see Table 1). In addition, they had normal (or corrected) vision and hearing; none of them had other neurological, genetic, nor psychopathological conditions. Comorbidities between the considered conditions (*i.e.*, DCD and NLD) constituted an exclusion criterion for the present study. None of the participants in the DCD, NLD, or ND groups met the criteria for autism using the ADI-R (Rutter et al., 2005) (Table 1). Similarly, none of the participants had comorbidities with ADHD, except for one child in the NLD group. A comorbid diagnosis of specific learning disorder was present for a few children in the DCD ($N = 4$) and NLD ($N = 5$) group. The three groups were not statistically different regarding chronological age [$F(2,99) = 2.156, p = .121, \eta_p^2 = 0.042$], gender distribution [$\chi^2(2, N = 102) = .327, p = 0.849, CramerV = 0.057$], nor vocabulary abilities [$F(2,99) = 0.209, p = .812, \eta_p^2 = 0.004$].

Participants with DCD had received an independent clinical diagnosis according to DSM 5 (APA, 2013) or ICD-10 (World Health Organization WHO, 1993) criteria. The diagnoses were also confirmed by administering a questionnaire to their parents, specifically devised to detect fine- and gross-motor impairments in children and adolescents (adapted from Henderson et al., 2007; Sparrow et al., 2016; Wilson et al., 2009). A more detailed description of the questionnaire is provided in the Supplementary Materials.

Children with NLD had received independent clinical diagnosis by private psychologists or psychiatrists at clinical specialized centres, with which the research team collaborates, following recommendations from the literature (Cornoldi et al., 2016; Fisher et al., 2022; Mammarella, 2022). For the inclusion in the study, once each family agreed to have their children considered as potential participant in the study, clinical reports and other available information (e.g., school record, observation notes taken during assessments, and summaries of clinical interviews) were reviewed by two of the authors ([blinded for review] and [blinded for review]). Only if both authors agreed that all the inclusion criteria were met, the families were notified and formally invited to take part in the research. Otherwise, they were informed that they did not meet the criteria for this study and thanked for their collaboration. For 27 out of 29 cases, the two authors achieved consensus independently, while for the remaining two cases, discrepancies were resolved through deliberative consultation. Moreover, clinical diagnoses of NLD were confirmed by the presence of deficits in visuospatial processing, observed by administering the Rey-Osterrieth Complex Figure Test (ROCFT; Rey, 1941, 1968).

Table 1

Characteristics of the groups with Developmental Coordination Disorder (DCD), Nonverbal Learning Disability (NLD), and typical development (ND).

Measures	DCD ($N = 29$) M (SD)	NLD ($N = 29$) M (SD)	ND ($N = 44$) M (SD)	Group significance ^e
Chronological age (months)	138.55 (26.28)	145.48 (31.82)	152.27 (25.84)	N.S.
Gender (M:F)	21:8	19:10	30:14	N.S.
Vocabulary ^a	11.34 (2.72)	11.48 (2.42)	11.11 (2.32)	N.S.
Block design ^a	10.79 (2.93)	7.24 (2.61)	12.02 (3.19)	NLD < DCD, ND
ROCFT: copy accuracy ^b	-0.95 (3.86)	-2.23 (2.42)	-0.54 (1.41)	NLD < ND
ROCFT: recall accuracy ^b	-1.18 (1.73)	-2.39 (1.74)	-0.40 (1.54)	NLD < DCD, ND
Fine-motor abilities ^c	17.14 (9.56)	15.32 (6.95)	6.18 (4.89)	DCD, NLD > ND
Gross-motor abilities ^c	18.62 (10.31)	8.64 (4.65)	4.95 (4.03)	DCD > NLD, ND
Reciprocal social interaction ^d	4.21 (2.91)	3.96 (2.85)	3.27 (2.46)	N.S.
Language/communication ^d	3.59 (2.16)	3.72 (2.10)	3.36 (2.31)	N.S.
Repetitive behaviors/interests ^d	0.97 (1.02)	1.10 (0.94)	0.91 (0.88)	N.S.

Note.

^a Scaled scores on the Vocabulary or Block design subtests from the WISC-IV (Wechsler, 2003).

^b ROCFT: Rey-Osterrieth Complex Figure Test (Rey, 1941, 1968), performances expressed as z scores.

^c Motor abilities questionnaire (adapted from Henderson et al., 2007; Sparrow et al., 2016; Wilson et al., 2009), higher raw scores reflect more severe impairments in fine and/or motor skills.

^d Raw scores on the Autism Diagnostic Interview- Revised (ADI-R, Rutter et al., 2005) domains.

^e Only significant comparisons are reported.

Children included in the ND group were recruited via local schools or community contacts. For these participants, DCD or NLD profiles were excluded by the administration of several screening measures, tapping both visuospatial processing and motor skills. The presence of any other neurodevelopmental disorder was excluded as well, as confirmed by a clinical interview conducted with the parents, which did not report any symptoms related to developmental atypicalities, either currently or in the participants' developmental history.

A summary of the sample's characteristics is provided in [Table 1](#), and a description of the screening measures is provided in the [Supplementary Materials](#).

The study received ethics approval from the institutional review board at the University of [blinded for review]. Participation in the study was conditional upon parents or legal caretakers signing an informed consent form; children were also explicitly asked to express their agreement to the participation.

2.2. Materials

2.2.1. Motor skills

The Movement Assessment Battery for Children–Second Edition (MABC-2; [Henderson et al., 2007](#)) was used to measure participants' motor abilities. The MABC-2 Battery covers three domains of competence, each of them with a specific set of tasks: Manual Dexterity (MD), Aiming and Catching (AC) and Balance (B). For each subtest and domain, raw scores were converted into scaled scores. Reliability is $r = 0.80$ for the MABC-2 total score, while ranging from $r = 0.73$ and $r = 0.84$ for each specific domain. A more detailed description of the MABC-2 tasks is provided in the [Supplementary Materials](#).

2.2.2. Visual-Motor Integration

The Developmental Test of Visual-Motor Integration (VMI; [Beery, 2004](#)) assesses visual-motor integration skills. Children were presented with a booklet containing 27 increasingly difficult geometrical figures and asked to reproduce them. Accuracy was computed by assigning one point for each correct reproduction. Raw scores were converted into scaled scores. Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.96$.

2.2.3. Visual-perceptual processing

The Overlapping Figures Test (adapted from [Bisiacchi et al., 2008](#)) was administered to assess participants' visual-perceptual abilities. Children were presented with a figure containing overlapping figures and requested to detect as many as they could within four minutes of time. Each correctly detected figure was awarded one point; raw score (i.e., sum of correctly detected figure) was used to perform analyses. Reliability is $r = 0.89$.

2.2.4. Spatial processing

The Animal Rotation task (adapted from [Kaltner & Jansen, 2014](#)) was administered to assess participants' mental rotation abilities. The task comprised 21 items: children were presented with a 2D target figure and asked to detect, among four alternatives, the only one that was a rotation of the target, within a 5-minute time limit. Each correct answer was awarded one point. Raw score was computed as a proportion of correct answers. Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.87$.

2.3. Procedure

Participants were tested individually either in a quiet room at the clinical centre where they were recruited, or in a laboratory provided by the University of [blinded for review]. All the administration and scoring of the tasks were carried out by licensed psychologists regularly registered with the national professional board, who had completed specialized post-graduate training in the diagnosis of neurodevelopmental disorders. The examiners had extensive experience in research on neurodevelopmental disorders and were blind to group membership when administering the tasks. Scoring was double-checked by two independent examiners and any inconsistencies were resolved.

Tasks were administered in two sessions, each lasting approximately 60 minutes. To avoid tiredness to interfere with the results, task administration followed a counterbalanced order.

2.4. Data analysis

Data analysis were conducted using R ([R Core Team, 2021](#)).

Firstly, descriptive statistics were computed, and analyses of variance (ANOVAs) were run, to highlight the existence of statistically significant differences between groups. Bonferroni's correction for multiple comparisons was used, when appropriate.

Second, the Area Under the Curve (AUC) of the ROC curve ([Robin et al., 2011](#)) was computed, aiming to estimate the discriminatory power of motor, visual-motor, visual-perceptual and spatial processing measures in distinguishing between clinical (i.e., DCD or NLD) and control groups. AUC were calculated taking into account measures of the following domains: motor skills (MD, AC and B from the MABC-2), visual-motor integration (i.e., VMI), visual-perceptual processing (i.e., Overlapping Figures Task), and spatial processing (i.e., Animal rotation task). Specifically, the AUC were computed by the comparison of the two clinical groups and of the ND group with the DCD or NLD group, respectively. The AUC ranges from 0 to 1.0: the higher the value, the better the diagnostic power of the test. An AUC = 0.70 could serve as a cut-off regarding the diagnostic power of a measure, meaning that such measure can detect approximately 70 % of the true positive cases. AUC values ranging from 0.80 and 0.90 suggest good diagnostic power, while an AUC

above 0.90 is considered excellent in their discriminating power (Zhu et al., 2010).

Complete analyses scripts are available at <https://osf.io/jqv6r>

3. Results

3.1. Preliminary analysis

In Table 2 descriptive statistics and statistical comparisons (ANOVA_s) between the three groups are summarized.

3.1.1. Motor skills

Different significant main effects of Group emerged for the three domains of the MABC-2. Overall, DCD participants scored significantly lower than ND participants in all the domains ($p_s < .001$). NLD group's performance was statistically different from those of the ND group in the Manual Dexterity domain ($p < .001$), while no statistically significant differences emerged between NLD and DCD groups ($p = .522$). Differently as for the Aiming/Catching and Balance domains, the NLD group's total scores fall between those of the DCD and ND groups, being statistically different from both: NLD group's scores were significantly lower than those of ND participants (AC: $p = .024$, and B: $p = .002$), and higher than those of the DCD group (AC: $p = .017$, and B: $p < .001$).

Descriptive statistics and the results of the Groups' comparisons between each single task composing the Movement ABC-2 indexes are provided in the Supplementary Material section (see Table S1).

3.1.2. Visual-Motor Integration

A significant main effect of group was found for the visual-motor integration task, with the NLD group performing worse than the DCD group ($p = .030$) that, in turn, performed worse than the ND group ($p = .001$).

3.1.3. Visual-perceptual processing

A significant main effect of group emerged for the overlapping figures test, showing lower scores for the NLD group compared to the ND group ($p = .002$).

3.1.4. Spatial processing

In the animal rotation task a main effect of group emerged, with lower scores for the NLD group as compared to the DCD and ND groups ($p_s < .034$).

3.2. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis

In Fig. 1 the results are summarized from the analysis of the AUC, ran comparing alternatively each group with another on motor, visual-motor, visual-perceptual and spatial processing measures.

As for the motor domain, the Manual Dexterity index showed good predictive power in discriminating between the ND group and the DCD or NLD groups ($AUC=0.85$ and $AUC=0.90$, respectively). Alternatively, this domain did not show sufficient predictive power in discriminating between the NLD and the DCD group ($AUC=0.63$).

The Aiming and Catching index also revealed a good predictive power in discriminating between the ND group and the DCD group ($AUC=0.83$), but not between the ND group and the NLD group ($AUC=0.69$) neither between the NLD and the DCD group ($AUC=0.68$). Overall, the Balance index revealed excellent predictive power in discriminating between the DCD group and the ND group ($AUC=0.97$), and good predictive power discriminating between DCD group and NLD group ($AUC=0.88$) yet revealing a weaker, but still significant, predictive power in discriminating between the NLD group and the ND group ($AUC=0.72$). More detailed

Table 2

Descriptive statistics and Analysis of the Variance (Univariate ANOVA_s) by group: Developmental Coordination Disorder (DCD), Nonverbal Learning Disability (NLD), and Typical Development (ND).

	DCD (n = 29) M (DS)	NLD (n = 29) M (DS)	ND (n = 44) M (DS)	F (2, 99)	p	η_p^2	Group significance ^a
Motor skills							
Manual Dexterity (MD)	4.14 (2.95)	3.07 (2.75)	8.59 (3.17)	35.70	< .001	.42	NLD, DCD < ND
Aiming and Catching (AC)	5.66 (3.67)	7.93 (3.14)	9.95 (2.49)	17.53	< .001	.26	DCD < NLD < ND
Balance (B)	4.34 (2.65)	8.97 (2.85)	11.09 (2.17)	63.49	< .001	.56	DCD < NLD < ND
Visuospatial skills							
Visual-Motor Integration	8.25 (2.36)	6.66 (2.21)	10.34 (2.36)	22.87	< .001	.32	NLD < DCD < ND
Visual-perceptual processing	25.22 (5.75)	22.99 (6.91)	28.52 (6.87)	6.47	.002	.12	NLD < ND
Spatial processing	0.85 (0.19)	0.69 (0.22)	0.84 (0.27)	4.31	.016	.08	NLD < DCD, ND

Note. Only significant comparisons are reported. Motor skills: Movement ABC-2 (Henderson et al., 2007); Visual-Motor integration: VMI (Beery, 2004); Visual-perceptual processing: Overlapping Figures Test (adapted from Bisiacchi et al., 2008); Spatial processing: Animal Rotation task (adapted from Kaltner & Jansen, 2014).

Fig. 1. Values of the area under the curve (AUC) of the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve, computed comparing alternatively each group with another on motor skills (manual dexterity, aiming and catching and balance), visual-motor integration, visual-perceptual and spatial processing.

results from the analysis of the AUC, taking into account each MABC-2 task, are provided in the [Supplementary Material](#) section (see [Figure S1](#)).

Considering visuospatial measures, the visual-motor integration task revealed a low but significant power in discriminating between the DCD group and the ND group ($AUC=0.74$). This task also revealed good predictive power in discriminating between the NLD group and the ND group ($AUC=0.88$). Differently, the comparison between DCD and NLD groups in this task revealed an AUC score

of .70, which is equal to the cut-off suggested by [Zhu et al. \(2010\)](#) for the interpretation of index's diagnostic power, not allowing a reliable interpretation of this result. As for the Visual-perceptual domain, the overlapping figures test revealed a low but significant predictive power in discriminating between the NLD group and the ND group ($AUC=0.73$), while did not reveal sufficient power in discriminating between the DCD group and the ND or NLD groups, alternatively ($AUC=0.62$). Finally, concerning the spatial processing domain, the animal rotation task showed a predictive power in discriminating between the NLD group and the ND or DCD groups ($AUC=0.75$ and $AUC=0.74$, respectively), while not accurately discriminating between the DCD and the ND groups ($AUC=0.57$). It is worth specifying that AUC 's indexes around .70, although statistically significant, should be interpreted with caution due to the large confidence intervals, which dampened the strength of their discriminative power.

4. Discussion

The present study aimed to analyze motor and visuospatial abilities in children with DCD or NLD, compared to peers without diagnosis, to better investigate possible overlapping symptoms. In fact, the common possession of challenges in transdiagnostic processes such as aiming and catching, and balance, along with visual-motor integration makes it difficult to fully differentiate DCD from NLD characteristics, thus determining a challenge in both the research field and clinical practices. Thus, it appears prominent to shed a broader light on specific strengths and weaknesses of each clinical condition. To address this issue, we firstly took into account similarities and differences in several motor and visuospatial domains. Secondly, the AUC of the ROC curves were calculated to estimate the discriminatory diagnostic power of the above-mentioned domains. The importance of cross-disorder comparisons in different neurodevelopmental disorders using a transdiagnostic approach, was recently highlighted. This may better serve our understanding of this large heterogeneous population ([Astle et al., 2022](#)). This is the first attempt to give an in-depth analysis on motor and visuospatial skills of both children diagnosed with DCD or NLD.

As for the motor abilities, our results have highlighted clinically significant scores for the group with DCD, consistently with previous research ([Blank et al., 2019](#)). Specifically, children with DCD underperformed ND peers, in all the three motor skills assessed. Moreover, the DCD group underachieved the NLD group in the two gross-motor tasks (aiming and catching and balance). In other words, the motor profiles of children with NLD appear to be heterogeneous, showing more severe difficulties in the manual dexterity domain and better performances in aiming and catching and balance. It is worth noting that, despite resulting lower than those of the ND group, the NLD group's average scores in these latter domains were at the lower boundary of the normal range, showing relatively spared gross-motor performances. The results upon manual dexterity corroborate the previous few findings identifying fine-motor weaknesses in this clinical group ([Durand, 2005](#); [Nichelli & Venneri, 1995](#); [Semrud-Clikeman et al., 2010](#)). Moving on from Fisher's systematic review (2022), stating the lack of studies describing the gross-motor profile in NLD, our results represent a significant contribution to the field by specifically describing a relatively preserved aiming and catching as well as balance performance within the NLD condition.

As for the visuospatial domain, a different pattern was observed. Unsurprisingly, the NLD group obtained the weaker performance in this task, compared to DCD and ND groups. In addition, weak visual-motor integration skills also emerged for children with DCD compared to their ND peers ([Van Waelvelde et al., 2004](#); [Wilson et al., 2013](#)), since children had to perceive visual input, process the information, and coordinate a motor response to correctly perform the task ([Carsone et al., 2021](#)). However, our findings revealed that visual-motor integration skills of children with DCD, although lower than that of the ND peers, can be considered relatively spared compared to that of the NLD group. In addition, typical performances in the tasks assessing visual-perceptual processing and spatial processing (as measured with a mental rotation task) were observed for children with DCD. On the one hand, this result is consistent with previous observations that have found no differences comparing groups with DCD or ND using similar visuospatial tasks ([Bonifacci, 2004](#)). On the other hand, it is in contrast with what emerged from other studies, showing impairments in visual-perceptual and spatial processing for children diagnosed with DCD ([Ameratunga et al., 2004](#); [Pisella et al., 2020](#)). As previously mentioned, Tsai and colleagues (2008) analysed in depth the visual-perceptual domain in children with DCD and revealed poorer performances than typically developing children. However, it is worth noting that only in two (*i.e.*, visual-form constancy and visual closure), out of seven subtests of the test-battery administered (*i.e.*, Test of Visual-Perceptual Skills-Revised; [Gardner, 1996](#)), a consistent number of DCD children (higher than 30 % of the sample) obtained scores in the clinical range (*i.e.*, below the 15th percentile). More recent findings reported heterogeneous visual-perceptual and spatial processing abilities in DCD, highlighting the need to further examine this argument ([Tsai et al., 2008](#); [Wilson et al., 2013](#)). In addition, as extensively discussed in the introduction section, methodological differences between the studies in the literature, which we tried to control and overcome in the present study, might in part explain the inconsistency in previous findings (*i.e.*, the presence of confounding comorbidity of developmental disorders ([Crawford & Dewey, 2008](#)); the requirement of visuospatial weakness as inclusion criteria (*e.g.*, [Gras et al., 2023](#)); groups matched only for age and sex (*e.g.*, [Tsai et al., 2012](#); [Van Waelvelde et al., 2004](#)) and not for IQ. Adversely, core visuospatial impairments emerged for children with NLD, tapping all the three sub-domains investigated (*i.e.*, visual-motor, visual-perceptual and spatial processing) and confirming their main characteristics, consistently with previous studies ([Fine et al., 2013](#); [Fisher et al., 2022](#); [Mammarella & Cornoldi, 2014](#)).

As for the discriminatory power, our results further support what emerged from the cross-disorder comparisons. As expected, motor skills effectively discriminate the DCD group's performance as compared to the non-diagnosed peers, while visual-spatial and manual dexterity skills accurately discriminate the NLD group's performances from those of the ND group. Notably, the comparison between DCD and NLD shows that balance emerges as a key factor for an effective discrimination between these clinical groups' performances. Additionally, spatial processing, albeit to a lesser extent, differentiated between groups. Taken together, our findings revealed cross-disorder similarities and highlighted specific hallmarks, corroborating the need to perform a comprehensive assessment of both motor and visuospatial abilities to discriminate between these conditions ([Gras et al., 2023](#); [Tsai et al., 2008](#)).

The present study provides new insights on similarities and differences involving motor and visuospatial profiles of children with a DCD or NLD diagnosis, but it involves some limitations that need to be mentioned. The first constraint is the predominantly male composition of the sample, which limits the generalizability of our findings to the females. Although a higher prevalence of males, rather than females, is reported in most of neurodevelopmental disorders (APA, 2013), it would be important for future research to better explore possible gender differences in the comorbid motor and visuospatial symptoms associated with these two conditions, as well as to pursue larger sample sizes to assess this issue. A second issue relates to the number of motor and visuospatial tasks we were allowed to administer. Further research should generalize the present results by also using different tasks, examining similarities and differences in motor and visuospatial profiles of children with DCD or NLD. Finally, the analyses were fully cross-sectional, which does not allow inferences to be drawn on individuals' developmental trajectories of motor or visuospatial skills. It would be interesting to carry out longitudinal studies in this regard.

Nonetheless, our findings have important clinical and educational implications. First, by providing novel insights upon each profile's specific features, our results expand the knowledge about the patterns of abilities and clinical hallmarks associated with these neurodevelopmental disorders. This could serve as a fundamental step towards the official recognition in the diagnostic manuals of conditions around which there is still limited exploration, such as NLD (Fisher et al., 2022; Mammarella, 2020, 2022). Second, our study underscores both the similarities and differences in the motor profiles of these two clinical conditions. Comparable fine-motor impairments, together with substantial differences in the gross-motor domain were observed, suggesting that balance and spatial processing may serve as key distinguishing features between DCD and NLD profiles. These domains should, therefore, be accurately taken into account when conducting differential diagnoses in clinical practice and when determining inclusion and exclusion criteria in future research.

In conclusion, our study enhances understanding of the transdiagnostic commonalities and distinct difficulties underlying the behavioral challenges observed in the daily life of children with neurodevelopmental conditions such as DCD and NLD. While anecdotal evidence and clinical observations have reported clumsiness and specific gross motor impairments in NLD children (Fisher et al., 2022), as well as research evidence of visuospatial difficulties in DCD (Gras et al., 2023; Sigmundsson et al., 2003), our findings clearly delineate two distinct profiles: those with balance, gross and fine-motor problems (*i.e.*, DCD), and those with fine-motor, visuo-motor and visuospatial processing difficulties (*i.e.*, NLD). At the same time, although there are boundaries between the two "categories", some symptoms attributed to one disorder may also occur, at varying levels of severity, in the other, in agreement with previous evidence on different neurodevelopmental disorders (Annaz et al., 2008; Thomas et al., 2009). Notwithstanding this, this is among the firsts studies directly comparing motor and visuospatial profiles of children diagnosed with NLD or DCD. Such obtained knowledge could represent a step forward in understanding and diagnosing children with either DCD or NLD, being in turn transferred to the design of treatment plans.

Ethics approval and consent to participate

The study was formally approved by the Institutional review board at the University of Padova, Italy. The procedures used in this study adhere to the tenets of the Declaration of Helsinki. Written informed consent was obtained from all the parents. Additionally, all children and adolescents assented to their participation in the study.

Authors' contributions

Conceptualization: Cardillo, Mammarella; Methodology: Cardillo, Orefice; Formal analysis and investigation: Cardillo, Orefice; Writing - original draft preparation: Cardillo, Orefice; Writing - review and editing: Cardillo, Orefice, Leanza, Mammarella; Supervision: Mammarella.

Statement

The authors would like to thank all the participants for their contribution to the study.

Funding

This research was co-funded by the Italian Complementary National Plan PNC-I.1 "Research initiatives for innovative technologies and pathways in the health and welfare sector" D.D. 931 of 06/06/2022, "DARE- Digital lifelong prevention" initiative, PNC0000002 – Spoke 2 - CUP B53C22006250001.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Irene C. Mammarella: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Camilla Orefice:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Ramona Cardillo:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Nicolas Leanza:** Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

Authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.ridd.2025.104922](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ridd.2025.104922).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Alloway, T. P., Rajendran, G., & Archibald, L. M. D. (2009). Working memory in children with developmental disorders. *Journal of Learning Disabilities, 42*(4), 372–382. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022219409335214>
- Ameratunga, D., Johnston, L., & Burns, Y. (2004). Goal-directed upper limb movements by children with and without DCD: A window into perceptuo-motor dysfunction? *Physiotherapy Research International, 9*(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pri.295>
- American Psychiatric Association [APA]. (2013). *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders* (Fifth Edition). American Psychiatric Association. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.books.9780890425596>
- Annaz, D., Karmiloff-Smith, A., & Thomas, M. C. S. (2008). The importance of tracing developmental trajectories for clinical child neuropsychology. In B. P. Rourke (Ed.), *Syndrome of Nonverbal Learning Disabilities: Neurodevelopmental Manifestations*. Guilford Press.
- Astle, D. E., Holmes, J., Kievit, R., & Gathercole, S. E. (2022). Annual Research Review: The transdiagnostic revolution in neurodevelopmental disorders. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry, 63*(4), 397–417. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcpp.13481>
- Basso Garcia, R., Mammarella, I. C., Tripodi, D., & Cornoldi, C. (2014). Visuospatial working memory for locations, colours, and binding in typically developing children and in children with dyslexia and non-verbal learning disability. *British Journal of Developmental Psychology, 32*(1), 17–33. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjdp.12019>
- Beery, K. E. (2004). *The Beery-Buktenica developmental test of visual-motor integration*. Pearson.
- Bisiacchi, P. S., Borella, E., Bergamaschi, S., Carretti, B., & Mondini, S. (2008). Interplay between memory and executive functions in normal and pathological aging. *Journal of Clinical and Experimental Neuropsychology, 30*(6), 723–733. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13803390701689587>
- Blank, R., Barnett, A. L., Cairney, J., Green, D., Kirby, A., Polatajko, H., Rosenblum, S., Smits-Engelsman, B., Sugden, D., Wilson, P., & Vinçon, S. (2019). International clinical practice recommendations on the definition, diagnosis, assessment, intervention, and psychosocial aspects of developmental coordination disorder. *Developmental Medicine Child Neurology, 61*(3), 242–285. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dmcn.14132>
- Bonifacci, P. (2004). Children with low motor ability have lower visual-motor integration ability but unaffected perceptual skills. *Human Movement Science, 23*(2), 157–168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.humov.2004.08.002>
- Bressel, E., Yonker, J. C., Kras, J., & Heath, E. M. (2007). Comparison of static and dynamic balance in female collegiate soccer, basketball, and gymnastics athletes. *Journal of Athletic Training, 42*(1), 42–46.
- Cameron, C. E., Cottone, E. A., Murrah, W. M., & Grissmer, D. W. (2016). How are motor skills linked to children's school performance and academic achievement? *Child Development Perspectives, 10*(2), 93–98. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdep.12168>
- Cardillo, R., Erbi, C., & Mammarella, I. C. (2020). Spatial perspective-taking in children with autism spectrum disorders: the predictive role of visuospatial and motor abilities. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience, 14*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2020.00208>
- Cardillo, R., Lanfranchi, S., & Mammarella, I. C. (2020). A cross-task comparison on visuospatial processing in autism spectrum disorders. *Autism, 24*(3), 765–779. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362361319888341>
- Cardillo, R., Vio, C., & Mammarella, I. C. (2020). A comparison of local-global visuospatial processing in autism spectrum disorder, nonverbal learning disability, ADHD and typical development. *Research in Developmental Disabilities, 103*, Article 103682. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ridd.2020.103682>
- Carsono, B., Green, K., Torrence, W., & Henry, B. (2021). Systematic review of visual motor integration in children with developmental disabilities. *Occupational Therapy International, 2021*, Article e1801196. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/1801196>
- Cattuzzo, M. T., dos Santos Henrique, R., Ré, A. H. N., de Oliveira, I. S., Melo, B. M., de Sousa Moura, M., de Araújo, R. C., & Stodden, D. (2016). Motor competence and health related physical fitness in youth: A systematic review. *Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport, 19*(2), 123–129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsams.2014.12.004>
- Chow, D., & Skuy, M. (1999). Simultaneous and successive cognitive processing in children with nonverbal learning disabilities. *School Psychology International, 20*(2), 219–231. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0143034399202005>
- Corbetta, D., Thelen, E., & Johnson, K. (2000). Motor constraints on the development of perception-action matching in infant reaching. *Infant Behavior and Development, 23*(3), 351–374. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0163-6383\(01\)00049-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0163-6383(01)00049-2)
- Cornoldi, C., Mammarella, I. C., & Fine, J. G. (2016). *Nonverbal Learning Disabilities*. Guilford Publications.
- Cornoldi, C., Rigoni, F., Tressoldi, P. E., & Vio, C. (1999). Imagery deficits in nonverbal learning disabilities. *Journal of Learning Disabilities, 32*(1), 48–57. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002221949903200105>
- Crawford, S. G., & Dewey, D. (2008). Co-occurring disorders: A possible key to visual perceptual deficits in children with developmental coordination disorder? *Human Movement Science, 27*(1), 154–169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.humov.2007.09.002>
- De Oliveira, J. A., Rigoli, D., Kane, R., McLaren, S., Goulardins, J. B., Straker, L. M., Dender, A., Rooney, R., & Piek, J. P. (2019). Does 'Animal Fun' improve aiming and catching, and balance skills in young children? *Research in Developmental Disabilities, 84*, 122–130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ridd.2018.07.004>
- Durand, M. (2005). Is there a fine motor skill deficit in nonverbal learning disabilities? *Educational and Child Psychology, 22*, 90–99.
- Farran, E. K., Bowler, A., Karmiloff-Smith, A., D'Souza, H., Mayall, L., & Hill, E. L. (2019). Cross-domain associations between motor ability, independent exploration, and large-scale spatial navigation; attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, Williams syndrome, and typical development. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience, 13*, 225. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2019.00225>
- Fine, J. G., Semrud-Clikeman, M., Bledsoe, J. C., & Musielak, K. A. (2013). A critical review of the literature on NLD as a developmental disorder. *Child Neuropsychology, 19*(2), 190–223. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09297049.2011.648923>
- Fisher, P. W., Reyes-Portillo, J. A., Riddle, M. A., & Litwin, H. D. (2022). Systematic review: Nonverbal Learning Disability. *Journal of the American Academy of Child Adolescent Psychiatry, 61*(2), 159–186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaac.2021.04.003>
- Gardner, M. F. (1996). *Test of Visual Perceptual Skills (Non-Motor) – Revised*. Psychological and Educational Publications.

- Gras, D., Ploix Maes, E., Doulazmi, M., Huron, C., Galléa, C., Boespflug Tanguy, O., Germanaud, D., & Roze, E. (2023). Developmental coordination disorder subtypes in children: An unsupervised clustering (n/a(n/a)) *Developmental Medicine Child Neurology*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dmcn.15563>.
- Jongmans, M. J., Smits-Engelsman, B. C., & Schoemaker, M. M. (2003). Consequences of comorbidity of developmental coordination disorders and learning disabilities for severity and pattern of perceptual—motor dysfunction. *Journal of Learning Disabilities*, 36(6), 528–537. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022219403036006040>
- Hegarty, M., & Waller, D. (2005). Individual differences in spatial abilities. In P. Shah, & A. Miyake (Eds.), *The Cambridge Handbook of Visuospatial Thinking* (pp. 121–169). Cambridge University Press.
- Hellendoorn, A., Wijnroks, L., van Daalen, E., Dietz, C., Buitelaar, J. K., & Leseman, P. (2015). Motor functioning, exploration, visuospatial cognition and language development in preschool children with autism. *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 39, 32–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ridd.2014.12.033>
- Henderson, S. E., Sudgen, D. A., & Barnett, A. L. (2007). *Movement Assessment Battery for Children: Second Edition (Movement ABC-2)*. The Psychological Corporation.
- Kaltner, S., & Jansen, P. (2014). Mental rotation and motor performance in children with developmental dyslexia. *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 35(3), 741–754. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ridd.2013.10.003>
- King, B. R., Kagerer, F. A., Harring, J. R., Contreras-Vidal, J. L., & Clark, J. E. (2011). Multisensory adaptation of spatial-to-motor transformations in children with developmental coordination disorder. *Experimental Brain Research*, 212(2), 257–265. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00221-011-2722-z>
- Loprinzi, P. D., Davis, R. E., & Fu, Y.-C. (2015). Early motor skill competence as a mediator of child and adult physical activity. *Preventive Medicine Reports*, 2, 833–838. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmedr.2015.09.015>
- Mammarella, I. C. (2020). The importance of defining shared criteria for the diagnosis of nonverbal learning disability. e202559–e202559 *JAMA Network Open*, 3(4). <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2020.2559>.
- Mammarella, I. C. (2022). Editorial: Time to recognize nonverbal learning disability to foster advances in its research. *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 61(2), 120–121. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaac.2021.05.015>
- Mammarella, I. C., Bomba, M., Caviola, S., Broggi, F., Neri, F., Lucangeli, D., & Nacinovich, R. (2013). Mathematical difficulties in nonverbal learning disability or comorbid dyscalculia and dyslexia. *Developmental Neuropsychology*, 38(6), 418–432. <https://doi.org/10.1080/87565641.2013.817583>
- Mammarella, I. C., Cardillo, R., & Semrud-Clikeman, M. (2022). Do comorbid symptoms discriminate between autism spectrum disorder, ADHD and nonverbal learning disability? *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 126, Article 104242. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ridd.2022.104242>
- Mammarella, I. C., Cardillo, R., & Zocante, L. (2019). Differences in visuospatial processing in individuals with nonverbal learning disability or autism spectrum disorder without intellectual disability. *Neuropsychology*, 33(1), 123–134. <https://doi.org/10.1037/neu0000492>
- Mammarella, I. C., & Cornoldi, C. (2005a). Difficulties in the control of irrelevant visuospatial information in children with visuospatial learning disabilities. *Acta Psychologica*, 118(3), 211–228. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actpsy.2004.08.004>
- Mammarella, I. C., & Cornoldi, C. (2005b). Sequence and space: The critical role of a backward spatial span in the working memory deficit of visuospatial learning disabled children. *Cognitive Neuropsychology*, 22(8), 1055–1068.
- Mammarella, I. C., & Cornoldi, C. (2014). An analysis of the criteria used to diagnose children with Nonverbal Learning Disability (NLD). *Child Neuropsychology*, 20(3), 255–280. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09297049.2013.796920>
- Mammarella, I. C., & Cornoldi, C. (2020). Nonverbal learning disability (developmental visuospatial disorder). In *Handbook of Clinical Neurology*, 174 pp. 83–91). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-64148-9.00007-7>
- Mammarella, I. C., Meneghetti, C., Pazzaglia, F., Gitti, F., Gomez, C., & Cornoldi, C. (2009). Representation of survey and route spatial descriptions in children with nonverbal (visuospatial) learning disabilities. *Brain and Cognition*, 71(2), 173–179. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bandc.2009.05.003>
- Mammarella, I. C., & Pazzaglia, F. (2010). Visual perception and memory impairments in children at risk of nonverbal learning disabilities. *Child Neuropsychology*, 16(6), 564–576. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09297049.2010.485125>
- Nichelli, P., & Venneri, A. (1995). Right hemisphere developmental learning disability: A case study. *Neurocase*, 1(2), 173–177.
- Orefice, C., Cardillo, R., Lonciari, I., Zocante, L., & Mammarella, I. C. (2024). “Picture this from there”: Spatial perspective-taking in developmental visuospatial disorder and developmental coordination disorder. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 15. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1349851>
- Petti, V. L., Voelker, S. L., Shore, D. L., & Hayman-Abello, S. E. (2003). Perception of nonverbal emotion cues by children with nonverbal learning disabilities. *Journal of Developmental and Physical Disabilities*, 15(1), 23–36. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1021400203453>
- Pisella, L., Martel, M., Roy, A. C., Vuilleumier, C., & Gonzalez-Monge, S. (2020). Validation of a simple screening test for elementary visuo-spatial perception deficit. *Annals of Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine*, 63(4), 302–308. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rehab.2019.03.006>
- R Core Team. (2021). *R: A language and environment for statistical computing [Software]*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing. (<https://www.R-project.org/>).
- Rey, A. (1941). L'examen psychologique dans les cas d'encéphalopathie traumatique. (Les problems.). [The psychological examination in cases of traumatic encephalopathy. Problems.]. *Archives Délétoit Psychologie*, 28, 215–285.
- Rey, A. (1968). *Epreuves Mnésiques et d'Apprentissage [Tests of Memory and Learning]*. Delachaux et Niestlé.
- Robin, X., Turck, N., Hainard, A., Tiberti, N., Lisacek, F., Sanchez, J.-C., & Müller, M. (2011). pROC: An open-source package for R and S+ to analyze and compare ROC curves. *BMC Bioinformatics*, 12(1), 77. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2105-12-77>
- Rosenberg, L., Moran, A., & Bart, O. (2017). The associations among motor ability, social-communication skills, and participation in daily life activities in children with low-functioning autism spectrum disorder. *Journal of Occupational Therapy, Schools, Early Intervention*, 10(2), 137–146. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19411243.2017.1304842>
- Rourke, B. P., & Strang, J. D. (1978). Neuropsychological significance of variations in patterns of academic performance: motor, psychomotor, and tactile-perceptual abilities. *Journal of Pediatric Psychology*, 3(2), 62–66. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jpepsy/3.2.62>
- Rutter, M., Le Coteur, A., & Lord, C. (2005). *ADI-R. Autism Diagnostic Interview- Revised*. Giunti O.S.
- Semrud-Clikeman, M., Fine, J. G., & Bledsoe, J. (2014). Comparison among children with children with autism spectrum disorder, nonverbal learning disorder and typically developing children on measures of executive functioning. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 44(2), 331–342. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10803-013-1871-2>
- Semrud-Clikeman, M., Walkowiak, J., Wilkinson, A., & Christopher, G. (2010). Neuropsychological differences among children with Asperger syndrome, nonverbal learning disabilities, attention deficit disorder, and controls. *Developmental Neuropsychology*, 35(5), 582–600. <https://doi.org/10.1080/87565641.2010.494747>
- Sigmundsson, H., Hansen, P. C., & Talcott, J. B. (2003). Do ‘clumsy’ children have visual deficits. *Behavioural Brain Research*, 139(1), 123–129. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-4328\(02\)00110-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-4328(02)00110-9)
- Soska, K. C., Adolph, K. E., & Johnson, S. P. (2010). Systems in development: motor skill acquisition facilitates 3D object completion. *Developmental Psychology*, 46(1), 129–138. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0014618>
- Sparrow, S. S., Cicchetti, D. V., & Saulnier, C. A. (2016). *Vineland Adaptive Behavior Scales—Third Edition*. Pearson. (<https://www.pearsonassessments.com/store/usassessments/en/Store/Professional-Assessments/Behavior/Adaptive/Vineland-Adaptive-Behavior-Scales-%7C-Third-Edition/p/100001622.html>).
- Staples, K. L., & Reid, G. (2010). Fundamental movement skills and autism spectrum disorders. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 40(2), 209–217. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10803-009-0854-9>
- Thomas, M. S. C., Annaz, D., Ansari, D., Scerif, G., Jarrold, C., & Karmiloff-Smith, A. (2009). Using developmental trajectories to understand developmental disorders. *Journal of Speech, Language, and Hearing Research*, 52(2), 336–358. [https://doi.org/10.1044/1092-4388\(2009\)07-0144](https://doi.org/10.1044/1092-4388(2009)07-0144)
- Tsai, C.-L., Chang, Y.-K., Hung, T.-M., Tseng, Y.-T., & Chen, T.-C. (2012). The neurophysiological performance of visuospatial working memory in children with developmental coordination disorder. *Developmental Medicine Child Neurology*, 54(12), 1114–1120. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-8749.2012.04408.x>
- Tsai, C.-L., Wilson, P. H., & Wu, S. K. (2008). Role of visual—perceptual skills (non-motor) in children with developmental coordination disorder. *Human Movement Science*, 27(4), 649–664. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.humov.2007.10.002>
- Van Waelvelde, H., Weerd, W. D., Cock, P. D., & Smits-Engelsman, B. C. (2004). Association between visual perceptual deficits and motor deficits in children with developmental coordination disorder. *Developmental Medicine and Child Neurology*, 46(10), 661–666. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0012162204001112>

- Wang, C.-H., Tseng, Y.-T., Liu, D., & Tsai, C.-L. (2017). Neural oscillation reveals deficits in visuospatial working memory in children with developmental coordination disorder. *Child Development, 88*(5), 1716–1726. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.12708>
- Wechsler, D. (2003). *Wechsler intelligence scale for children—Fourth edition (WISC-IV)*. The Psychological Corporation.
- Wilkinson-Smith, A., & Semrud-Clikeman, M. (2014). Are fine-motor impairments a defining feature of nonverbal learning disabilities in children? *Applied Neuropsychology: Child, 3*(1), 52–59. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21622965.2012.712823>
- Williams, J., Thomas, P. R., Maruff, P., Butson, M., & Wilson, P. H. (2006). Motor, visual and egocentric transformations in children with Developmental Coordination Disorder. *Child: Care, Health and Development, 32*(6), 633–647. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2214.2006.00688.x>
- Wilson, B. N., Crawford, S. G., Green, D., Roberts, G., Aylott, A., & Kaplan, B. (2009). Psychometric properties of the revised Developmental Coordination Disorder Questionnaire. *Physical Occupational Therapy in Pediatrics, 29*(2), 182–202.
- Wilson, P. H., Ruddock, S., Smits-Engelsman, B., Polatajko, H., & Blank, R. (2013). Understanding performance deficits in developmental coordination disorder: A meta-analysis of recent research. *Developmental Medicine Child Neurology, 55*(3), 217–228. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-8749.2012.04436.x>
- Wilson, P. H., Smits-Engelsman, B., Caeyenberghs, K., Steenbergen, B., Sugden, D., Clark, J., Mumford, N., & Blank, R. (2017). Cognitive and neuroimaging findings in developmental coordination disorder: New insights from a systematic review of recent research. *Developmental Medicine Child Neurology, 59*(11), 1117–1129. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dmcn.13530>
- World Health Organization [WHO]. (1993). *The ICD-10 classification of mental and behavioural disorders*. World Health Organization.
- World Health Organization [WHO]. (2022). *International classification of diseases and related health problems* (11th revision). (<https://icd.who.int/en>).
- Zhu, W., Zeng, N., & Wang, N. (2010). Sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, associated confidence interval and ROC analysis with practical SAS® implementations. *NESUG proceedings: Health Care and Life Sciences, 19*, 67.
- Zwicker, J. G., Harris, S. R., & Klassen, A. F. (2013). Quality of life domains affected in children with developmental coordination disorder: A systematic review. *Child: Care, Health and Development, 39*(4), 562–580. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2214.2012.01379.x>